

Astro Data Archive Tape Drive Project

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Observations at Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) and Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) obtained from May 1987 to September 2000 were archived to 8mm data tape for long-term storage. During this period approximately 9300 tapes were written, for a total of ~ 50TB of scientific data. The tapes closely resemble those used in consumer video camcorders from that time (Figure 1). This recording technology is now obsolete, and up until just recently, millions of science observations contained within the tapes were “dark data” and at risk of being lost forever.

The data in the tapes are still scientifically useful and thus worthy of recovery and proper archiving. For instance, the Mayall legacy Mosaic-1 observations are similar to the contemporary Mosaic-3 data, facilitating direct comparison of object changes over time. These data also have historical significance. According to astronomer Dr. Tod Lauer, “The tape archive contains the original images used by two separate teams to discover the effects of ‘dark-energy’ on the expansion of the Universe (in short, by discovering supernova that were used as ‘standard candles’ to assess distances to galaxies over extremely large scales). These observations revolutionized modern cosmology and were recognized with three Nobel prizes in physics in 2011.”

8mm tape technology has been abandoned since the late 1990s, and therefore the hardware needed to transcribe data has become increasingly scarce. That, in combination with the threat of physical tape degradation, means that permanent data loss is imminent. These factors provided the urgency to design and implement the Tape Data Rescue Project (TDRP).

A timely opportunity presented itself at NSF’s NOIRLab in collaboration with the American Astronomical Society (AAS). The AAS Archive Fellowship was created for a quarter-time graduate student to work on both the Abt Archives and the TDRP. The Abt Archives is a physical collection of approximately 35,000 manuscript files related to *The Astrophysical Journal* (ApJ) during the editorship of Helmut A. Abt (NOAO, ret.), who served from 1971 through 1999 using a manual, paper-intensive review process. These two projects are preserving aspects of our astronomical heritage by conserving, organizing, and making important archival collections available.

The TDRP was initiated in 2019 with a computer workstation connected to 20 recycled exabyte tape drives. Progress halted at the start of the COVID-19 pandemic and resumed in 2021. The initial reading of all of the primary tapes was completed by 2022. During this period many

Figure 1: The picture shows the galaxy M81 imaged in the lines of H-alpha and [OIII] with the Mosaic-1 camera on the Mayall 4-meter telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory. The observations were from 23 exposures and 3 proposals taken between 2001 and 2002 and recovered from the Save-the-Bits tapes (Seaman 2000). The image is from 1/8th of the wide-field camera. The color composite is rendered with H-alpha in red, [OIII] in blue, and green from the narrowband continuum near [OIII]. The emission lines are characteristic of HII regions that produce the many pink/blue/violet features in the star-forming arms of M81. One value of the recovered Mosaic data is the large selection of filters used over the roughly four years of tape archived data. *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/F. Valdes/T. Rector*

tape drives failed and had to be replaced with “creative procurements” from various surplus equipment markets. Physical tape failure also occurred many times throughout the process of reading tapes.

Analysis of the retrieved data revealed that some degradation of the tapes had taken place since they had been written 20–30+ years ago. Some tapes had files with either partial or complete data corruption. Fortunately, the effects of tape degradation were mitigated by redundant tape copies stored at mountaintop facilities. A final accounting of the recovery success rate is pending.

Despite numerous logistical challenges, the TDRP is nearly complete and will soon be publicly available. Some

recovered datasets have already been delivered to the original PIs. Data are currently being characterized and prepared for public release via the [Astro Data Archive](#), part of the Community Science and Data Center. Dr. Frank Valdes is using existing pipeline software to perform basic calibration to produce science-ready images (Figure 2). According to Dr. Valdes, “Our ability to calibrate these data, both in terms of quality and computational speed, has advanced, and so the archived calibrated images produced from these imagers will be state-of-the-art.”

Reference

Seaman, R. L. 2000, *ASPC*, 216, 133

Figure 2: 9300 8mm tapes stored in cabinets at NOIRLab Headquarters, Tucson, Arizona. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/R. Faux